

The Contribution of Electronic Marketing in the Increment of Grape Sales in Dodoma

A Study of Bihawana and Mpunguzi Village

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Abstract:- The study sought to examine the contribution of e-market in increment of grape sales in Tanzania. Was specifically sought to determine the effect of e-mail, mobile phones-advertisement and ICT on sales for grape farmer in Dodoma. Number respondents (70) who are farmer used selected based on simple random sampling. Data gathered by filled questionnaires were coded, tabulated and analyzed using STATA version 12 by descriptive statistics based on frequencies and percentage used to present cross tabulate. The study results indicated that few number of grape farmers use e-marketing This is attributed to the fact that many farmers do not possess the ICT skills as well as ICT tools to be used in e-marketing. It was concluded that the farmers need to be facilitated with these required tools. And farmers have to be taught about electronic market variable that affects the sales of grape Recommend is training about marketing and the way of accessing the marketing information by using of e marketing tools. The obstacle of the study is the farmer are not knowing what were ask and the study based on Dodoma villages further researcher will based on other product how affected by Electronic market in Tanzania.

Keywords;- Marketing , Electronic -Marketing, Grape, Farmers And Dodoma.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ Background to the Study

This study looked into the role of e-marketing on the increment of grape sales in Dodoma. This is due to fact that electronic marketing is rapidly becoming a new phenomenon in modern business practice at this days when internet dominates (Taylor et al., 2018).According to world grape farming data, grape production was 477,909.28 thousand tons in 2018,and is 18% of total fruit production worldwide(FAO, 2018).. However European Union takes the lead in grape production, with Italy leading by15.48 percent, followed China with 15.73 percent, and United States with 11.93% (FAO, 2018).

Between the years 2010 and 2018, FAO show grapes had been rising in global market and made a significant contribution to the economy of various countries in world. VinIntel (2014) and Stephen (2017) both found that grape sales has increased as a result of wine production.

South Africa is the world's largest grape and wine in African also the world's seventh largest grape and wine producer, with over 100,000 hectares of land dedicated to grape cultivation (VinIntel, 2014). South Africa's grapes and wine are primarily export to Europe (VinIntel, 2014).

In Tanzania missionaries introduced grapes Dodoma in 1960 at Bihawana and farming of grape in start in 1963, Isanga prison began to produce grapevine with four acres (Daily News, 25th November 2011). After three years the crop was transferred to Mpunguzi, Msalato, Nala, Nkulabi, and Mundemu village's. As a result, the National Service was established. Start increasing the acreage and the yields rising high from the grapes used for fresh table to wine production. The first government institution to invest much in wine production was Isanga prison which prompted the construction of a winery plant in 1969 a company was the sole buyer of grapes from farmers for wine processing (VinIntel, 2014). Due to this the government establishments of a Makutupora Research Centre to determine appropriate types of grapes of wines and encouraged more and more farmers to come forward and open grape farms (VinIntel, 2014).

Marketing is an important aspect in developing countries that increased investment, but grape producers faced difficult to participate in markets due to increased market freedom pressures (Makhura, 2001). Nonetheless, grape production and sales in the Dodoma is increasing, despite the face with both chances and obstacles (Kacharo,2007). According to this point of view, it shows that the evolution of digital marketing necessitated many businesses to engage on digital platform in selling and marketing of their Products and Services and such traditional marketing functions are becoming being minimized (Monnapa, 2017).

➤ Statement of the Research Problem.

The world has become the use of digital that lead to electronic marketing is a major area of interest in business entities as they are force to undertakings (Adikesavan, 2015).

However, despite the buzz word that e-marketing it is easy and good strategy of marketing, there is still little knowledge about how it is used in business circles, especially in the areas of farmer and the consumer of grape in Tanzania. Most of the studies so far conducted with regard to e-marketing and its role in business have been undertaken in Tanzania (Ngowi, 2015). However, many study like VinIntel, (2014). Makhura, (2018) and Kacharo, (2007) tell about the market situation and challenge face of grape in Dodoma the study looks how practical knowledge of used electronic market tools that to ass’s market information of grape and the theoretical knowledge of how to accept the new market strategy of e-marketing of grape for farmer of grape in the village. the outcome of this study will lead to the uses of electronic device to market grape which lead increase of spread information and sales of grape also it can educate the farmer about the issue of global market

➤ *Purpose of this study*

The study was to examine the contribution of e-marketing in increment of grape sales in Tanzania.

➤ *Objectives of the study*

The objective was based on look the relationship between electronic marketing and increment of grape sale

➤ *Limitation of the study*

The study was focus on the uses of electronic marketing of a farmers to the increment of sale of grape in two village of Dodoma region of mpunjguzi and bihawana and the uses of internet to many farmer was a new knowledge so it was difficulty when you collect data du farmers are not understand what was ask .

II. LITERETURE REVIEW

The study was used a theory in regard to electronic marketing is Technology Acceptance Model Propagated by Davis (1986), the Technology Acceptance Model as an information systems-based theory shows the behaviors behind the acceptance of use of technology for various activities; the knowledge of the model is that in any new technology is introduced, there are factors that come into play before that technology is started used by the people among of the factor One is the how usefulness of that technology. The degree to which an individual person believes that by using that particular technology, this would eventually enhance someone’s performance of the work (Davis ,1986). in this study of the uses of the form of e marketing like e mail, mobile phone and e advertisement purchasing to sell the grape in Dodoma at mpunguzi and bihawana . Another key component of the TAM is the perceived ease-of-use, which according to Davis (1989), entails the extent to which an individual believes that that using a particular system would not entail a lot of efforts (Davis, 1989).

The application of TAM to this study in regard to its two elements: perceived usefulness of that technology and ease of use. In the use of TAM is relevant to this study given the way it is applicable to farmer of grape to in the uses of electronic marketing tools (form) to sell grape. Farmer they have consider how easy of used e market tools in the daily ways of marketing of grape (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980)

➤ *Empirical Literature Review*

Trendo,(2019) the study of digital technology in agriculture and rural area of Italy Rome that aim to identify the different process of digital transformation in a rural area it identify that the education , infrastructure and network support the digital transformation and factor that can for the adaptation of technology is production the used a case study design but the weakness is not show the impact the marketing information

Tertell (2018) the study of precision agriculture monitoring system in Germany using green internet of thing the existing of the agriculture application help in increase the production of crop because the study used of email to send mail to the farmer how are in a group about the how the right time emitting gas , pest control in a green housing but they have a challenge of adopt this because farmer are not familiar in uses of application

Panda (2019) the study of the role of the mobile phone in agriculture and allied activity of rural house hold in India most farmer in the county are small in nature the study it is show how is the difficulty to provide information to many farmer so the uses of mobile phone will provide easy way of get information by using many application of agriculture which provide the information about weather and price of input the weakness is they base of the use of mobile phone in advisor of farmer not used has promotion tool.

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

A graphically showing the relationship of independence and dependent variable variables (Miles & Huberman, 1994). This study investigates the contribution of electronic marketing form usage form in the increment sales of grape.

Source: Researcher through literature review (2021)

The table show the measurement of conceptual framework Conceptual Definition (s), Measurement (s) and Source (s)

Variable (independent variable)	Measurement	Sources
E-mail	Do you used e marketing to marketing grape 1.yes 2.no	Grape farmer
Mobile phone (social media)	Do you have mobile phone 1 yes 1.no if yes used in marketing	Grape farmer
E – advertisement	Do u know e advertisement 1.yes 2 .no if yes do you used e advisement for marketing of grape	Grape farmer
Ict	Do you know information communication technology (ict) has a search engine 1. Yes 2. No if yes do you have a skill used computer and used that ict has form of searching engine to market	Grape farmer

But if the answer is yes in variable it shows the increment of grape sale if is no it show the uses of traditional method that lead to grape market problem.

III. METHODOLOGY

The sample for the study was a farmer of the grape at Dodoma city in mpunguzi and bihawana village totally of 70 farmers was get by raosoft online chosen by simple random selection.

➤ *Data collection method*

The primary data was collected by Self-administered questionnaires were distributed to seventy (70) respondents who filled them and the researcher administered filling process

➤ *Statistical tools*

The data was collected by questioner and put into cross tabulated. A pilot study was done to checked questioner and the analysis of data the validity and reliability of questioner measured by a pilot study was of the farmers whereby questionnaires were distributed to 10 respondents in order to identify questions that might be unclear or ambiguous to them. The data was analyzed by quantitative methods which data was coded, edited, and analyzed statistically by using STATA software version 12 based on descriptive statistics of frequency and percentage that will show relationship between variable that presented for interpretation and summarized in tables and pie charts followed by short and brief explanations of the contents so as to fulfill the objectives of this study.

➤ *Ethical considerations*

For ethical requirements in the conduct of the study respondents were duly informed of the fact that the study was for academic purpose and that they were under no compulsion to respond to the questionnaire. The respondents were asked to participate voluntarily whilst assuring them of anonymity and confidentiality on the information given. In order to avoid plagiarism, all sources of information were duly acknowledged.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Distribution of respondents according to demographic characteristics*

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	40	57%
Female	30	43%
Age		
Below 20 years	8	11.4%
20-50 years	48	68.5%
Above 50 years	14	20.1%
Marital status		
Single	36	51.4%
Married	25	35.7%
Divorced	4	5.7%
Widowed	5	7.2%
Education		
Primary education	23	32.8%
Secondary Education	26	37.1%
Certificate	10	14.2%
Diploma	8	11.4%
Bachelor	5	7.1%
Above bachelor	3	4.2%
Farming experience		
1-10 years	17	24.3%
11-20 years	43	61.4%
21 and above	10	14.3%

Source: Field data (2021).

➤ Findings according to specific objectives

1. Using E-mail in marketing Grapes

	Frequency	Percentage
E-mail usage	20	32.8%
Traditional marketing	50	67.2%
Total	70	100%

Source: Research Data (2021)

2. Using Mobile Phones (smart phones) as e-marketing tool for Grapes

	Frequency	Percentage
Mobile (smart) Phone usage as e-	19	27.1%
Traditional marketing	51	72.9%
Total	70	100%

Source: Research Data (2021)

3 Using E-advertisement as e-marketing tool for Grapes

	Frequency	Percentage
E-advertisement as e-marketing	19	27.2 %
Traditional marketing	51	72.8%
Total	70	100%

Source: Research Data (2021)

4 Using ICT as e-marketing tool for Grapes

	Frequency	Percentage
ICT as e-marketing tool	18	25.7%
Traditional marketing	52	74.3%
Total	70	100%

Source: Research Data (2021)

➤ Analysis of result and discussion.

Frequency table of Distribution of respondents according to demographic characteristics. Was showing the Age of Respondents majority of grapes farmers (68.5%) of all respondents who participated in the study were in age between 20 and 50 years, Marital Status of the Respondents majority are 51.4% single, showed that 32.8% of grapes farmers have primary education and The Experience of the Farmers it showed that 61.4% of farmer are experience of 11 to 20 years of farming of grape.

➤ Analysis according to specific objectives

1 Frequency table of Using E-mail in marketing Grapes results showed that 32.8 % of grapes farmers use e-mail to market grapes while majority of 67.2% uses normal traditional techniques. This can be attributed to the lack of new technology skills or lack of the accessories like smart phone or computers which facilitates usage of emails.

2 Frequency table of Usage of Smart Phones in marketing of the Grapes results showed that 27.1 % of grapes farmers use smart phones which can access marketing information and send to the user in the process of marketing their grapes while majority of 72.9% uses normal traditional techniques This can be attributed to the lack of new technology skills or lack of the smart phones.

3 frequency table of Usage of E-advertisement in marketing of the Grapes⁴ results showed 27.2% of grapes farmers use e-advertisement which can access marketing information and

send to the user in the process of marketing their grapes while 72.8 % uses normal traditional techniques

4 frequency table of Using ICT as e-marketing tool for Grapes⁵ results showed that ICT is used by only 25.7% of grapes farmers while 74.3 % uses normal traditional techniques. Therefore, the results obtained implied that among the two villages only small number of respondents have a knowledge and ability of using ICT to market their products. The low percentage is attributed to the fact that most farmers do not possess electronic like computers, smart phones and lack of skills on how to use ICT.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, four independent variables which are, usage of emails, usage of smart mobile phones, usage of e-advertisement and usage of ICT by farmers, are the factors which affecting the grapes marketing which resulted in increment of sales in Dodoma region. These four significant variables are the factors affecting e-marketing of grapes in Dodoma. Policy Implications towards the grapes marketing in the country may help to improve the growth of sales of grapes market in Dodoma in order to get reliable market e-mails, smart phones, e-advertisement and ICT are the very important factor hence implies that there should the improved technology should be taught to grape farmer.in other way experience farmer should increase their skills and knowledge on the use of technology on how to contact the customers. Also the study was Recommend training and workshop must be provided to a farmer in order to build they are knowledge of marketing by using electronic marketing and further study be done in other product and in a different area out of grape and mpunguzi and bihawana village in Dodoma

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